

Sustainability for the Watershed Management in Afghanistan: Example from Amu River Basin

Safiullah Sherzad*¹, Tharavathy Nidya Chennappa²

¹Biosciences Department, Mangalore University, India.

Email: safisherzad7@gmail.com | ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1325-2226>

²Biosciences Department, Mangalore University, India.

Email: tharabiosciences@gmail.com | ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5194-6635>

*Corresponding Author

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Abstract

The Amu River Basin, located in northeast Afghanistan, is the second largest basin. Therefore, a general concept of the importance and value of watershed management has been reviewed. Too little water at a given time can be a disaster (e.g., draughts), and too much water available at the same time is also a tragedy (e.g., in the form of floods). Sustainable water management needs to have a moderate water flow, maintenance of the water quality, mitigation of water flows to minimize soil erosion, recharging of groundwater, and conservation and recycling. This paper will help understand the different elements and aspects of watershed management in Afghanistan and its interactions with technology, economics, institute, and natural resources. The importance of contributing to water and land management is linked with the people's livelihood.

Keywords

Watershed management; Sustainability; Amu River

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Introduction

Afghanistan is a country whose water depends on snow and permanent glaciers in the highlands. These glaciers form rivers as a result of melting of the ice. Global warming, climate change, and other environmental issues have become more serious for nations and governments. Afghanistan, too, has not been an exception and has become more vulnerable, because of a lack of awareness and expertise, and a fragile economy that have led to less attention being paid to water. Therefore, in the current situation, the seasonal rains must be managed to the extent possible. However, the present Afghanistan government has weaknesses politically, and economically. Therefore, to assess the current challenges of watershed management is necessary.

In the 21st century, the world environment is facing severe challenges, such as (i) competing water demand for basic necessities such as food, (ii) the convergence of urban population and increasing water demands, (iii) dependence of energy sector on urban water infrastructure, (iv) water infrastructure development, particularly in the developing countries, and (v) essential threats posed by climate change (Feilberg and Mark, 2016). Therefore, effective and sustainable watershed management needs emphasis in order to achieve holistic development. A set of technologies can provide exciting opportunities and solutions. Afghanistan is a country that has plenty of natural waters, especially in the Amu Darya watershed. Per capita water availability is 4,250 cubic meters per year in Amu River basin. The country's internal freshwater resources per capita show that Afghanistan has sufficient water availability. However, Afghanistan is a country that has experienced many years of war, and the wars imposed by foreign countries have prevented Afghanistan from achieving its development plans. After 1970, Afghanistan decided to manage its water. At that time, it needed to manage water on a larger scale in order to strengthen agriculture and the energy sector; but, due to the constant wars, it did not happen. Today, after 50 years, Afghanistan has lost almost entire infrastructure like irrigations canals, Kariz and semi-elapseds dams and canals preventing it from achieving its plans. Moreover, given the current climate change, economic downturn, and political turmoil in Afghanistan, the country cannot implement its large-scale projects. Therefore, sustainable resource management, especially water, soil and energy, is essential, and a comprehensive solution is needed. This article discusses how to use and manage water effectively for sustainable production and conservation.

Study Area

The Amu basin is one of the five river basins in Afghanistan. It is part of the Amu Darya basin, a share of the larger Aral Sea basin that covers Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Most of the rivers in Afghanistan have shared water with their neighboring countries, except for the Kunar River basin. All the big rivers in Afghanistan originate from the highland region of central mountains (Hindokush) and northeastern mountains (Pamir). Amu River basin in Afghanistan is located in the northeast of the country, which covers four provinces (Badakhshan, Baghlan, Kunduz and Takhar) shown in figure 1.

The classical name of the Amu Darya is "Oxus River," which has a large number of tributaries with a 2,400 km length in central Asia. It dries up into the Turan lowland in Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. The main course irrigates cotton fields; but 20 years back, the river water ran to as far as the Aral Sea. Today, lack of water or inflow has been one of the significant problems reducing surface area and capacity of water in the Aral Sea. The headwater of the Amu River basin started from the High Pamir Mountains of Afghanistan and Tajikistan. Zor Kul lake is the northern branch of the Amu Darya, called the Ab-i- Pamir River, and the outflow of Chakmatin lake is the southern branch of the Amu River. The Amu River basin covers 57% of the total water flow and covers only 14% of Afghanistan with all its drains. Therefore, the Amu river basin has a significant potential for water development and management that has been unused till now (Sergei and Langford, 2002).

Figure 1: Area of the Amu River Basin in Afghanistan

Sustainable Management

The sustainable development has different definitions. Yet, the common purpose of sustainable development is to meet the need of the present generation in such a way that it does not forego the resources needed for future generations. Thus, sustainable management promotes the minimization of the environmental impact and optimal use of the resources (Farooq *et al.*, 2005). Watershed management in Afghanistan is an important solution to address sustainability issues. The watershed management will also be helpful in addressing the global warming, poverty, and political deprivation of local people.

A general concept of sustainable watershed management is described with river basin's sustainability and the dimensions of technology, institutions, economics of natural resources in figure 2.

Figure 2: Sustainability of watershed management and its elements

Four main elements shown in figure 1 need to be considered for sustainable watershed management. The four elements are natural resources, technology, institutions, and economics. Each element has different components to analyze its functions and contributions toward sustainability (Vishnudas, Fletcher and Ladson, 2005).

Natural Resources

Natural resources in each country vary according to its geographical location. Afghanistan has an average altitude of 2,000 meters above sea level. The country's water comes from seasonal snow and rain, which is rich and fresh. Afghanistan has five maritime basins, the Kabul River, the Helmand River, the Harirod Murghab River, the Northern River, and the Amu River Basin. The Amu River basin also has a common border between Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan, and Afghanistan has the second-largest share of the river after Tajikistan, at about 27 billion cubic meters. According to the of Afghanistan's Ministry of Energy and Water, Afghanistan's surface and groundwater resources are 80 billion cubic meters per annum. Unfortunately, due to a lack of proper management, this water resource is minimally used for improving the production processes. The Ministry of Energy and Water explained that surface water has reduced from 57 billion cubic meters in 2003 to 49 billion cubic meters in 2018 (Aini, 2007). The reasons for such a reduction of water are: (i) Climate change; (ii) Population increase; (iii) Increase of hot days and decrease of cold days during a season.

Afghanistan is currently experiencing a series of droughts, with the lowest snowfall compared to previous years. Seasonal rains do not occur at the right time, and damaging floods often accompany the rains (Aini, 2007). This causes financial and human life losses; floods have also created soil erosion, which is a problem in itself.

Land Use and Watershed Management

The Amu River in the North of the country has formed about 1,200 kilometers of shared border between Afghanistan and the three countries - Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan. Therefore, the first goal of integrated watershed management is to provide services and goods maintaining the long-term production capacity of natural resources. People want to have numerous goods and services from the watershed, including water for irrigation, hydropower, drinking water, crops, dairy products, meat, wood products, raw materials, biodiversity, tourism, and recreation. Based on the localized topographic regime and the ecology, the objectives of integrated watershed management should include:

- increasing water and improving the quality of water in lakes, streams, and other water bodies;
- sustaining the existing environment and resources for managing, developing, and sustaining production systems;
- enhancing the potential of land and reducing downstream sedimentation, and preventing excessive soil erosion;
- rehabilitating the degraded wetlands, stream channels, watershed lands, and riparian systems.

Water and soil conservation represents the core element of watershed management; therefore, many objectives are related to the water and soil conservation practices. However, the integrated watershed management approach distinguishes from other land management practices as the watershed management have holistic linkages. How these linkages affect the sustainability of the natural resource depends on what demand people raise (Bochet, Rubio and Poesen, 1998). Therefore, planning for the efficient and effective/sustainable use of water, land, and other resources is needed to achieve integrated watershed management goals.

Interactions of Land Use

The Amu River Basin originates from the four provinces of Badakhshan, Baghlan, Kunduz, and Takhar in Afghanistan, usually the Great Pamir Mountains of Badakhshan Province and the Hindu Kush Mountains of Baghlan Province. In terms of the geological structure, Badakhshan has altitudes higher than 7,000 meters above sea level, which usually has less agricultural land. However, the same geological structure is available in other districts of Takhar and Baghlan. The interconnections of land use with water and other natural resources in the watershed's boundaries can be in many different ways. The watershed can be thought of as a collection of land use units of changing physical size. Relations between the rest of the watershed and a land-use unit are conceptual. Note that any activities in the upstream land-use units influence the land-use unit's downstream productivity (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2010). These influences may affect the soil loss/erosion rate; sediments downstream may consequently change the water flow patterns, soil quality, and water availability in the downstream watershed. Such phenomenon can impact human health, family incomes, and food availability (Dovers, 2001). Various management practices related to water, land, and other resources should be implemented in the downstream land-use unit (figure 3). They may be impacting the sustainability and productivity of the natural resources on site, and may be associated with livestock grazing, agriculture, or forestry, or allied activities.

Figure 3: Interactions of land-use in a watershed [Source: Gergersen, Ffolliott and Brooks (2007)]

Finally, the watershed management practices on the land-use unit can affect water quality, soil erosion, sediment movements, and water flows.

Availability of High-Quality Water

The water demands depend on what people want to do. Therefore, it is difficult to provide high quality water with constant supply for the welfare and survival of people. Too little water at a given time can be a disaster (e.g., draughts), and too much water available at the same time is also a disaster (e.g., floods). Hence, sustainable water management demands a moderate water flow, maintaining the water quality, mitigating water flows to minimize soil erosion, recharging groundwater, and preventing the water pollution (Dewald

et al., 1996). Managing and developing watershed management plays a critical role in increasing high-quality water supply to improve food security or other welfare for downstream watershed areas particularly. In developing countries, the watershed/water management with other associated resources development also links with poverty alleviation. There are often two primary responses when the water demand increases, as illustrated in figure 4. Unfortunately, in many parts of the world, reducing per capita consumption to conserve water resources has had limited utility in meeting people's demands. However, several methods have been used to develop water supplies without a locally dependable perennial stream or abundant groundwater resources – the other primary response.

The structural and non-structural measures should be an array in high flows, and the extreme flooding area for its coping and control are shown in figure 4. However, the issues associated with the patterns of water flow in terms of both low and high elevation, the stated purpose of structures such as reservoirs and dams are to control the floods and store the floodwater. Therefore, the non-structural approach to control the impacts of flooding through effective flood management is where the focus was placed on minimizing flood hazards.

Amu River Basin in Afghanistan

The Amu River basin has a population of approximately 4.2 million and per-capita water availability of 4,250 m³/year, well above the water stress threshold. Therefore, agriculture is by far the largest water user in the basin. As a result of mild climate combined with relatively high precipitation, most parts of Afghanistan would be classified as having a dry climate with cold winters. Abundant river flows and fertile soils, in the lower part of the basin, especially in the lower Kunduz, Taloqan, and Panj Amu basin, have been one of the breadbaskets of Afghanistan since 1930 the area was developed. The basin has been the largest wheat producer, with over 1.28 million tons (of which 1.0 million tons are from irrigated areas) produced in 2015, and the largest rice producer, with 263,000 tons produced in 2015¹. The total irrigated land in the basin is 450,000 ha², representing approximately 4.7% of the total surface area of the basin. However, more than 40 years of war and social conflict have resulted in poor management of both watershed areas and irrigation systems, causing serious problems of water management, especially irrigated agriculture, and a very significant drop in productivity. While, despite being a large food producer, the basin has some of the highest incidences of food insecurity (the food insecurity index is as high as 73% in the provinces of Badakhshan and Baghlan³).

Table 1: Internal freshwater resources per capita (cubic meter) in Afghanistan

Year	1962	1967	1972	1977	1982	1987	1992	1997	2002	2007	2012	2017
Water per capita	5042	4533	3998	3579	3659	4063	3252	2435	2086	1739	1513	1299

Source: World Bank - Renewable internal freshwater resources per capita (cubic meters)⁴

The estimated the freshwater resources per capita every five years is shown in table 1. In 1960 Afghanistan had 8,996,967 population, and the water per capita was 5,042 cubic meters per year, whereas in 2017, the country's population increased to 36,296,111 where the water per capita decreased by 1,299 cubic meters per year. According to Daniel (2018), Afghanistan population in 2050 will be about 64,682,974. In 2050, per capita water availability will decrease to 450-500 cubic meters only. Consequently, demands, challenges, and conflicts, especially in the urban area, will increase. Therefore, watershed management becomes essential from the perspective of rejuvenating of the resources.

¹ Government of Afghanistan, Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock, Agricultural YearBook 2015.

² World Bank, 2014, Afghanistan Agricultural Sector Review.

³ Central Intelligence Agency, 2014. World Factbook, 2014-2015 (52nd Edition), Washington.

⁴ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ER.H2O.INTR.PC>

Figure 4: Responses to the increased demands for water [Adapted from Gergersen, Ffolliott and Brooks (2007)]

Figure 5: Freshwater per capita during the years 1962-2017 [Source: World Bank - Renewable internal freshwater resources per capita (cubic meters)⁵]

Afghanistan has five river basins: the Amu River basin, Kabul River basin, Helmand River basin, Northern River basin, and Harirod-Murghab river basin. The total number of existing dams on these five river basin is 21, which currently generate 310 MW of electricity. These dams irrigate around 5,82,000 hectares of land. Harirod-Murghab river basin is the largest in terms of irrigated area of 3,04,000 ha, and the Kabul River basin is the most significant in term of electricity generation of 2,06,000 MW (Qureshi, 2002). Afghanistan government has 133 ongoing and 89 proposed dam projects in the Amu River basin executed by Ministry of Rehabilitation and Development. Additional 2 ongoing and 12 planned projects belong to the Ministry of Energy and Water, along with 11 ongoing and 9 planned projects from the Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock. In the Amu River basin, 12 electricity-generating dams costing \$ 1,075 million are designed to produce 115 MW electricity and irrigation of 1,32,848 ha of land. The dam's names and locations are shown in table 2.

Technology

The sustainable technologies need to be transferred, adopted, and developed (Guerin, 2001). The main challenge for sustainable development is land degradation. On a global scale, the key threats to the sustainability of life support systems are the availability of water, soil degradation, and loss of biodiversity (Hurni, 2000). Through using appropriate technology, natural resources can potentially be used sustainably. In addition, sustainable technology requires that a technology should be economically productive, ecologically conducive, financially viable, socially acceptable, and risk-reducing (Hurnai, 1998). Some innovative measures in watershed management can be taken through using appropriate technologies, such as tillage techniques e.g., stone bunds, terracing, grass contours, etc. Thus, successful adaptation of such a technology by the farmers is necessary before choosing technologies compatible to environments and land uses.

Watershed management covers water, forestry, soil, and agriculture management, so technology remedies for managing these resources may succeed only when they address local socio-economic needs (Azab *et al.*, 2021). However, rarely do farmers adopt the technologies recommended by experts. Technologies intended to develop the sustainability and productivity of medium/small farming systems should ideally be low cost, simple, maintainable, productive, flexible, low-risky, and runoff-reducing (Lambin and Megfroidt, 2010).

⁵ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ER.H2O.INTR.PC>

Moreover, technologies must be accessible, relatively more labor-intensive than capital intensive, triggering more intense local involvement, and generating more employment (Shah, 2002).

Table 2: 12 electricity and irrigation dams in the Amu River basin

No.	Project Name	Province	Years	Cost in Million \$	Power Generation Capacity (MW)	Irrigable Area (Ha)	Net Present Value ⁶ (NPV)
1.	Warsaj Irrigation & Hydropower	Takhar	1983	300	45	40,000	46,299,751
2.	Kelagai Irrigation & Hydropower	Baghlan	1981	444	54	54,187	15,085,804
3.	Zardalo Storage Dam Irrigation	Takhar	1984	7	0	5,000	14,731,289
4	Aish Aab Storage Dam	Badakhshan	2015	16	0	4,000	3,294,547
5	Tangi Nahrin Storage Dam	Baghlan	2015	11	0	2,000	-1,011,451
6	Anjoran Irrigation & Hydropower	Badakhshan	1984	80	15	5,281	-3,651,511
7	Korsom Storage Dam	Bamyan	2016	11	0	1,500	-3,635,241
8	Hasantal Irrigation	Baghlan	1984	78	0	15,000	-4,534,888
9	Tagab Ghar Storage Dam	Bamyan	2016	11	0.5	500	-5,232,956
10	Chal Storage Dam Irrigation	Takhar	2015	10	0	120	-8,212,947
11	Char Dara Irrigation	Kunduz	1981	57	0	5,000	-28,592,847
12	Gazak Storage Dam Irrigation	Bamyan	2015	51	0.7	260	-37,868,168
Total				1,075	115	132,848	

Source: Ministry of Rural Rehabilitation and Development (MRRD) and Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation, and Livestock (MAIL)

Institutions

In context of an operation, the integration means inter-sectoral interaction of different departments through using an interdisciplinary approach while addressing the use and management of resources, and poverty reduction (Mollinga, 2000). All the shared efforts are mediated through institutions, and, without institutional change, it is challenging to move purposefully towards sustainability (Dovers, 2001).

⁶ Net present value (NPV) is the difference between the present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflows over a period of time. NPV is used in capital budgeting and investment planning to analyze the profitability of a projected investment or project. NPV is the result of calculations used to find today's value of a future stream of payments. Read more at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/n/npv.asp>

Institutions act as game changer in society, and organizations may be thought of as the groups of individuals bound together by some common purpose to achieve defined objectives (North, 1990).

For successful watershed management, the roles of strong institutions at the grassroots level are crucial. Two kinds of institutions are needed in watershed management to link or frequently interact with each other: (i) those involving internal stakeholders, and (ii) those involving external stakeholders (Longanandhan *et al.*, 2020). The first one is the community level self-help group, watershed committee, or user group. These community level institutions need to be federated to empower primary stakeholders at the watershed level to access an opportunity for collective action (Brose, Williams and Martinez, 2006). The second group of institutions involves external agencies such as non-government organization (NGO), government departments, researchers, and local administration. Example can be WDT (watershed development team) functioning at macro- or micro-watershed level.

Table 3: Water Sector Institutional Arrangement (various lines of Ministries directly involved in water sector projects)

No.	Official Agency	Responsibility as Part of SCWAM Institution
1.	Ministry of Energy and Water	In charge of developing and managing water resources and water resources infrastructures (diversion and conveyance of water) and hydropower.
2.	Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation, and Livestock	In charge of developing and managing irrigation agriculture and livestock, on-farm water management, water application to crops.
3.	Ministry of Urban Development	In charge of policy making and legislation of urban water supply and sanitation.
	Afghanistan Urban Water Supply and Sewerage	In charge of management and operation of urban water supplies in cities.
4.	Ministry of Mines	In charge of underground water resources management, survey, investigation, discovery and development, and control.
5.	Ministry of Rural Rehabilitation and Development	In charge of rural water supplies and sanitation and small-scale irrigation (village level) and rural micro hydropower projects.
6.	Ministry of Public Health	In charge of regulating and monitoring the quality of (drinking) water.
7.	National Environment Protection Agency	In charge of regulating and monitoring any activity related to the environment, including water.
8.	Kabul Municipality	As a representative of the capital city, it is a member of the SCWAM.
9.	National Hydrology Committee for Afghanistan (NHCA)	Advisory, research activities, and capacity building support to the water sector.
10.	Dehsabz City Development Authority (DCDA)	In charge of feasibility study and design of water supply and discharge systems for the New City at Dehsabz.

In 2005, the First Vice President of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan created the Supreme Council for Water Affairs and Management (SCWAM), which was composed of the following government of Afghanistan (GoA) officials: 1) Ministry of Energy and Water, 2) Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock, 3) Ministry of Urban Development, 4) Ministry of Rural Rehabilitation and Development, 5) Ministry of Mines, 6) Ministry of Public Health, 7) Ministry of Economy, and 8) Mayor of Kabul. The

creation of SCWAM clearly recognized the significance of water and the development of the national economy.

In addition, there are numerous lines of ministries that are directly not involved in the water/watershed management projects, but, through their assigned responsibilities, facilitate the standard functionality of the water sector.

Table 4: Government institutions indirectly involved in the water sector

No.	Official Agency	Responsibility as Part of SCWAM Institution
1.	Ministry of Interior	Any dispute on water-related conflicts referred to this ministry and security measures.
2.	Ministry of Justice	Clarification and elaboration of water law and regulations.
3.	Ministry of Finance	Proper funding of water sector activities will be of essential importance.
4.	Ministry of Economics	Evaluation of the impact of WRD on the national economy and prioritization of projects.
5.	Ministry of Women's Affairs	Necessary inputs and technical guidance as to addressing women's issues and gender agenda within the water sector.
6.	Ministry of Counter Narcotics	Funding of projects in the water sector, advisory support and capacity on CN issues, and providing input to the National Water Resources Development Plan.
7.	Provincial Governments and Development Committees	Help and support for establishing river basin councils according to water law and its regulations and help in their function and activities.
8.	Ministry of Higher Education	Developing curriculum for WRM, support human resources development in the water sector.

Economics

A new technology or a measure for water and soil conservation must be economically viable; otherwise, it will be hard for society to accept it. Even if that technology or measure fulfilled the needs of all other facets of sustainability, if economically not viable, it will fail (Prinz and Singh, 2000). Therefore, investment in new technologies benefits people only if adoption rate is high (McCulloch, Meinzen-Dick and Hazell, 1998). Though, traditional conservation practices have higher rate of adoption, better production needs innovative conservation measures (Thapa and Paudel, 2004). Further, if the adopted technology is economically viable, the economic return covers all the farmer's input. Therefore, while designing the numerous structure of water and soil conservation, it is essential to know the income of the households that will choose to invest in maintaining water and soil conservation practices (Walsh, Fletcher and Ladson, 2009). The decision of families to intensify their crop production and the adoption of water and soil conservation has to improve output per unit area through an increased labor or capital investment. Water and soil conservation measures must inflict chance of costs through their demands in labor (Vishnudas, Fletcher and Ladson, 2005). Investment in water and soil conservation does not result in higher income in the short time, but it generates returns in the long term; therefore, investing in water conservation is automatically beneficial without looking in detail at the costs and benefits. Therefore, related to economic sustainability, there is affordability and cost-effectiveness with the various activities in the watershed projects.

The construction material and labour costs should be conducive for adopting innovative technology because farmers cannot adopt the soil conservation techniques that require high investments. Farmers would adopt

conservation measures only if economic revenues are attractive apart from low construction costs or labour costs (Thapa and Paudel, 2004). Moreover, using local materials and local labour can increase the output of fodder and crops for their livelihood. Since the Amu River Basin shares water with the northern border countries of Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan, water management often involves conflict (Omerkhil *et al.*, 2020). Hence, global geopolitics has defined water conflicts, negotiations, management, cooperation, and resource development. The negotiations resolving water conflicts can be helpful in evolving a mechanism sustainable water management (Atef *et al.*, 2018). Thus, watershed management technology has a suitability to be effective in transboundary water management, soil fertility development, soil protection and poverty reduction (Groninger, Ruffner and Walters, 2013). *In situ* moisture conservation (trenching, bund cum trench and water absorption), rainwater collection (farm pond, percolation tank and check dam), and soil conservation (continuous contour trench, earthen bund and pebble Bunding) are useful techniques to conserve water (Reddy, Shaharawat and George, 2017).

Conclusion

The Amu River Basin has a good water capacity and is also very instrumental in developing agriculture and energy production. However, the available capacity of the Amu River area has not been used because of economic and political problems, and the lack of a clear and comprehensive agreement between the neighboring countries involved in the water has caused the plans not to be implemented at an appropriate time. Therefore, the current needs for watershed management are to manage snow, rain, and flood water differently, which means managing a relatively small amount of rainwater that the downstream area is not to be affected. Therefore, the sustainability of watershed management and integrated watershed management needs to be introduced in the region so that people can be involved in water management projects. The four elements considered for the integration of watershed management in this article should first be introduced to local people to be aware of the importance of water and the impact of water management on their daily lives and the local economy.

This article focuses on water availability and sustainability in context of maintaining environmental assets. To manage the natural resources, policymakers and water managers must clearly understand the natural environment and the water system's interactions. The elements discussed for better watershed management in this article indicate that we can do inordinate work for small watershed management purposes. The technology or technique used to manage the watershed should be discussed with the local people first in order to satisfy them. Farmers and local people should be more interested in encouraging or introducing this technology/technique. The technology to be implemented must be economical, and the local people can do it easily and without the need for more skills. All these factors together can save and manage natural resources such as valuable water.

Economically, new technologies should be cost-effective and affordable; labor and costs must be conducive to embracing innovative technology because farmers cannot adopt soil conservation techniques that require high investment. Farmers use conservation measures only if their economic returns are attractive apart from low labour costs. The government departments, including the Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock, and National Environment Protection Agency, should use agricultural extension staff to raise awareness about the importance and protection of soil, water, and natural resources. In addition, the extension of agriculture and the environment can help local people to adopt new technology.

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Authors' Declarations and Essential Ethical Compliances

Authors' Contributions (in accordance with ICMJE criteria for authorship)

Contribution	Author 1	Author 2
Conceived and designed the research or analysis	Yes	Yes
Collected the data	Yes	No
Contributed to data analysis & interpretation	Yes	Yes
Wrote the article/paper	Yes	No
Critical revision of the article/paper	yes	Yes
Editing of the article/paper	Yes	No
Supervision	No	Yes
Project Administration	Yes	Yes
Funding Acquisition	No	No
Overall Contribution Proportion (%)	60	40

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